

**IMPACT OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY ON
ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE
(A CASE STUDY OF HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY IN NIGERIA)**

BY

**FAJEMILUA BEN OLAREWAJU
P19DLBA80482**

**MBA PROGRAMME/FACULTY OF ADMINISTRATION
DISTANCE LEARNING CENTER,
AHMADU BELLO UNIVERSITY, ZARIA,
NIGERIA**

OCTOBER, 2023

Title Page

**IMPACT OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY ON
ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE
(A CASE STUDY OF HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY IN NIGERIA)**

BY

**FAJEMILUA BEN OLAREWAJU
P19DLBA80482**

**A THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE FACULTY OF BUSINESS
ADMINISTRATION, DISTANCE LEARNING CENTRE, AHMADU BELLO
UNIVERSITY, ZARIA, NIGERIA, IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT FOR THE
AWARD OF MASTER OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION (MBA).**

OCTOBER, 2023

DECLARATION

I declare that this dissertation titled: “Impact of Information Communication Technology on Organizational Performance (A Case study of Hostility Industry in Nigeria).” was written by me. The information derived from the literature has been duly acknowledged in the text and a list of references provided. No part of this Project report was previously presented for another Certificate, Degree or Diploma at this or any other Institution.

FAJEMILUA BEN OLAREWAJU
P19DLBA80482

13/10/2023

DATE

CERTIFICATION

This project report entitled: “Impact of Information Communication Technology on Organizational Performance (A Case Study of Hospitality Industry in Nigeria)” by Fajemilua Ben Olarewaju meets the regulations governing the award of Master in Business Administration, and is approved for its’ contribution to knowledge and literary presentation.

Dr. Hauwa Abdullahi Mustapha

Project Supervisor

Prof. Mohammed Ibrahim Sule

Director, Distance Learning Centre

Prof. M.N. Shuaibu

Dean, SPGS

DEDICATION

This research is dedicated to God Almighty for His Mercies upon my life.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT.

I would like to express my gratitude to my supervisor, Dr. Hauwa Abdullahi Mustapha, for her subtle but firm guidance and contributions to the completion of my research work.

Special appreciation goes to my chairman: the executive chairman of Royal Resorts Ibadan; HRM Oba Abiodun Kola-Daisi for his financial support while commencing the MBA program.

I cannot but thank my dear wife, Mrs. Anuoluwapo Mosunmola Fajemilua who stood by me and encouraged me all the time at a point that I almost gave up on the continuation of the MBA program. My Dad's follow-up from the beginning to the end of the program was overwhelming.

I appreciate my children; Ire, Tommy and Moyo for their understanding through this time-taking and tasking academic venture.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Contents

TITLE PAGE	i
DECLARATION	ii
CERTIFICATION	iii
DEDICATION	iv
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	v
TABLE OF CONTENTS	vi
LIST OF TABLES	ix
LIST OF FIGURES	x
ABSTRACT	xi

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1	Background to the Study	
1.2	Statement of the Problem	
1.3	Research Questions	
1.4	Objectives of the Study	
1.5	Statement of Hypotheses	
1.6	cope of the Study	
1.7	Significance of the study.	
1.8	Limitations of the Study.	
1.9	Definition of terms.	

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1	Introduction.	
2.2	Concept of IT and Performance of Organisations	
2.3	Organisational Performance.	

2.4	The Hospitality Industry in Nigeria
2.4.1	Hotel Reservation Systems.....
2.4.2	Property Management Systems.....
2.4.3	Yield Management Systems.....
2.4.4	The use of Search engine optimization (SEO).....
2.4.5	Social Media and Internet Marketing
2.5	Empirical Review.....
2.6	Theoretical Framework.....
2.7	Conceptual Framework.....

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1	Introduction
3.2	Research Design
3.3	Population of the Study.....
3.4	Sample Size and Sampling Technique.....
3.5	Method of Data Collection.....
3.6	Method of Data Analysis.....
3.7	Validity and Reliability of Instrument.....

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1	Introduction.....
4.2	Response Rate.....
4.3	Preliminary analysis.....
4.4	Outliers.....
4.5	Normality test.....
4.6	Common method bias.....
4.7	Non-response bias test.....

4.8 Multicollinearity.....

4.9 Assessment of Path Model.....

4.9.1 Measurement Model.....

4.9.2 Structural Model.....

4.10 Coefficient of determination (R^2).....

4.11 Effect size (f^2).....

4.12 Predictive Relevance Assessment (Q^2).....

4.13 Discussion of Findings.....

CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction.....

5.2 Summary.....

5.3 Conclusion.....

5.4 Recommendations.....

5.5 Limitations of the Study and Suggestions for Further Study.....

References

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3.1:	Sample Frame and Sample Size.....
Table 4.1:	Questionnaire Distribution and Response Rate.....
Table 4.2	Total and Percentage of Missing Values.....
Table 4.3:	Results of Independent Samples T-Test for Non- Response Bias.....
Table 4.4:	Collinearity diagnostic: Correlation and Variance inflation factor (VIF).
Table 4.5:	Item Loadings, Internal Consistency, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE).
Table 4.6:	Discriminant Validity using Fornell and Larcker Criterion.....
Table 4.7:	Measures and Threshold Values for Assessment of Inner Model.....
Table 4.8	Path Coefficient.....
Table 4.9	Coefficient of Determination (R^2).....
Table 4.10:	Effect Size (f^2).....
Table 4.11:	Predictive Relevance(Q^2).....

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework.....	
Figure 4.1: Normality of Data Using Histogram.....	
Figure 4.2: Measurement Model.....	
Figure 4.3: Structural Model.....	
Figure 4.4: Predictive Relevance.....	

ABSTRACT

The adoption of information technology in operations helps reduce operations costs and improve operational efficiency. The aim of this study is to ascertain the influence of information technology on the organizational performance of firms in the Nigerian hospitality industry. To achieve these objectives, the study employed a cross-sectional descriptive survey. Data was collected using a semi-structured questionnaire from starred hotels in Nigeria. A total of 200 questionnaires were administered to 100 hotel firms, but the researcher managed to obtain 181 completed questionnaires representing a response rate of 90.5%. The researcher adopted an online survey–form approach where questionnaires were sent using email then the results were available immediately after every respondent finished answering questions. The study found that hotel reservation system, property management system and yield management system have positive significant effect on organisational performance of hospitality industry in Nigeria.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Information technology plays a major role in the tourism, travel and hospitality industry. The integration of ICT in the tourism industry is essential for the success of tourism enterprises. IT facilitates an individual to access product information from anywhere at any time, and can also reach the targeted customers across the globe with a single click on the keypad through the use of mobile computers and web technologies (Bethapudi, 2013). Over the years, technology in business has been changing rapidly as the global environment becomes highly competitive and innovative. In particular information technology has become very vital to all organizations that intend to remain competitive in the market. The drivers of change in today's world include deregulation, global excess capacity, global competition, changing customer expectations, IT, demographic shifts and changing work and lifestyles. These changes have led organizations to embark on activities that will provide a source of competitive advantage and embrace the usage of IT (Shi, Alastair & Kevin, 2006). Organizational performance is measured for different levels of hierarchy and can be assessed for individuals, groups, and the entire organization as a whole (Knies, Jacobsen & Tummers, 2016). This is done by reviewing and optimizing the operations of the business units, through dedicated information technology solutions. One of the clearest definitions of Organizational performance describes it in terms of the growth and survival of the firm (Etzioni, 1960; Chandler & Hanks, 1993). In this definition, a firm may consider its performance to be effective if it is able to meet its prescribed goals and continue to improve. Organizational performance reviews can help companies identify areas of opportunity for improvement and provide insights regarding current employees' capabilities and skills. Learning how to measure and improve an organization's performance can help hospitality firms leverage their available resources to achieve set goals (Indeed Editorial Team, Nov. 11 2022). In a

multivendor environment, it is essential to understand the division of services into basic IT services and application management services. Basic IT includes, for example, network services, server services, workstation services as well as a service desk for user queries and problems. The continual service improvement proposals accepted by the business are transferred to service production through service design and service transition. Furthermore, continual service improvement includes preparing for changes in the IT operating environment (DiRomauldo & Gurbaxani, 1996).

Information and communication technologies (ICTs) are necessary components of business culture. In today's world using ICT is no more distinctive characteristic by itself, only an effective and efficient usage can help in obtaining a competitive advantage. When the right technology is available and it is correctly applied, a manager can obtain visible organizational benefits and is able to stimulate the growth of the company, in line with the market evolution.

The travel and tourism sector are known to be one of the world's largest and enduring industries. Its revenues support a significant proportion of the economies of Nigeria and it is one of the largest employers worldwide. Its contribution to gross national product, employment and regional development are well documented and, unlike many other sectors, it is forecast to grow in importance in the coming decades as leisure time increases. Tourism is acknowledged to be very information intensive. This sector is also open to the elements of the fragmentary developments in the information and communication technologies (ICT) field. The exchange of information is very important at every stage in the sales cycle of the tourism product or service. Information must be able to flow quickly and accurately between the client, intermediaries and each of the tourism suppliers involved in servicing the client's needs. As a result, ICT (Information Communication Technology) has become an almost universal feature of the hospitality industry. Its power allows information to be managed more effectively, and transported worldwide almost instantly. As a result, it has had (and continues to have) a major effect on the methods of operation of the hospitality industry (Nwakanma, 2014). The uses of information communication

technology have made possible the speed and efficiency with which information of the hospitality industry is developed, stored and recovered. Today hospitality is among the most important application domain in the World Wide Web. Demand for hotel information is becoming increasingly complicated and the hospitality industry employees have to learn how to use the modern technology so as to respond correctly to a wide range of needs in the industry. With the help of information communication technology (ICT), people can now go online and receive instant information for their holidays, hotels travel arrangement and booking e.t.c. The internet technology continues to have effect in promoting the sharing of information, making possible rapid transaction among businesses and supporting global collaboration among individuals. To some organizations, the innovation of internet has become a source of accommodation reservation for the hospitality industry there-by increasing the sales of rooms; with the internet the rate turnover tended to increase, compared to personal contact. For instance, Royal Resorts Ibadan Limited, Oyo State, one of the hospitality providers today has integrated into its management various ICT database management and multimedia systems.

The emergence of global system for mobile telecommunication (GSM) has truly made communication dissemination less stressful to both guests and the management within areas of operation. Thus, both domestic and international guests have opportunity to possibly enquire about existing product and costs offered for items.

ICT continues to have a profound effect in promoting the sharing of information, making possible rapid transaction amongst businesses. Hence this research work set out to investigate Impact of Information Communication Technology on Organizational Performance (A Case Study of Hospitality Industry in Nigeria)

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Information technology attempts to improve the quality of goods and services offered, through cost management, time service delivery and improve processes and procedures. According to Porter and Tanner (2012), the development of IT has had profound effects on goods and services

marketing. Traditionally IT facilities were primarily used for general business applications such as data entry, analysis and manipulation of that data for reporting purposes (Kim, Eves& Scarles, 2013). Information technology is a key growth area in this century, especially in a dynamic business and high-competition environment, which requires utilizing, advanced IT tools to improve efficiency, and cost-effectiveness and to present high-quality products and services to customers (Seethamraju, 2012). Global studies focus on IT implementation, management and success in more developed countries like America and China (Davenport, 2013). Competition and dynamic business environments have also triggered studies to evaluate the extent of use in various industries. However, little attention is given to information technology and the organizational performance of firms in the Nigerian hospitality industry. Mihalic and Buhalis (2013) studied ICT as a new competitive advantage factor; a case of the small transitional hotel sector. This study contributed to the knowledge of IT competitiveness and IT productivity paradox in the hotel sector but did not focus on the effects of IT on organizational performance. Appaw and Agbola (2013) study on 9 uses of IT in the front office operations of hotel chains in Ghana addressed how hospitality industry firms can take advantage of the pervasiveness of IT tools vis-à-vis technology-based systems to advance some of the operations. The study has shown the need to study IT effects on the organizational performance of firms in the Nigerian hospitality industry. Monge and Fulk (1999) in their study on the effects of IT network connectivity factors on the organizational performance of commercial banks; wanted to establish the connectivity factors and their effects on operations. However, the study only focused on IT networks and left out other key IT aspects. There have been several studies on the effects of IT-supported operations on service quality in Nigeria. The purpose of this study was to establish the effects of IT on service quality but failed to address key organizational performance concepts of firms in the hospitality industry. It is evident that IT has been given more emphasis as a collection of systems rather than a tool for improving organizational performance. In reference to all these studies, there is partial indication that superior use of IT leads to improved firm performance, the factors through which this is

achieved are by no means clear. Additional research is therefore needed to identify the underlying factors connecting IT to organizational performance.

1.3 Research Questions

In line with the problem, the following research questions were raised:

- i To what extent does hotel reservations systems affect organisational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria?
- ii. To what extent does property management systems affect organisational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria?
- iii. To what extent does yield management systems affect organisational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The study seeks to achieve the following two objectives.

- i. To determine the impact of hotel reservations systems on organisational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria.
- ii. To identify the impact of property management systems on organisational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria
- iii. To determine the impact of yield management systems on organisational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria

1.5 Research Hypotheses

To achieve the research objectives, the following hypotheses have been formulated:

H₀₁: Hotel reservation system does not have significant effect on organisational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Property management system does not have significant effect on organisational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Yield management system does not have significant effect on organisational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study focused on the impact of ICT on organizational performance, using the hospitality industry in Nigeria as a case study. The decision to use the hospitality industry in Nigeria as a unit of analysis was informed by the fact that the hospitality industry is one of the key industries its functionality depends greatly on the use of ICT and the study used primary data that were collected through a structured questionnaire.

1.7 Significance of the Study

Management teams will use the findings as the base upon which to review their company performance. Necessary improvements identified could be undertaken to enhance performance at the workplace.

The findings can also be used by human resource management to help in boosting employee performance at various workplaces.

The findings of the study will be of assistance to the government in setting the standards that hotels should work towards meeting if our hotels are to remain competitive in the world market and also for the improvements in service delivery in the industry.

The use of IT will assist in monitoring hospitality operations and more critically, improve the level of security measures under the modern-day threat of terrorism.

The regulators and the policymakers can use the finding as a reference for policy guidelines on information technology and human resource management in the hospitality industry. They will be able to use the findings of the study to formulate viable policy documents that effectively will in turn boost productivity.

1.8 Limitations of the Study

The study will consider ICT as a factor external to the hotel and analyze managers' perceptions of the way their internal systems should respond to the requirements imposed by ICT. For the purpose of this study the internal elements of the hotels, such as corporate culture and working processes, will be considered as a picture-perfect totality which changes in response to the presence of ICT.

1.9 Definition of Terms

This study involves several key concepts. The way these key terms are defined for the purpose of this study is considered below.

IT (Information Technology): is the use of computers to create, process, store, retrieve and exchange all kinds of data and information.

Hotel Reservation System: is a tool that is used by hotels to allow guests to make easy, secure, direct reservations online.

Property Management Systems: systems that facilitate the day-to-day operations of any accommodation business such as reservations, front desk, housekeeping, maintenance, billing and revenue data analytics.

Yield Management Systems: a data management, analysis, and tool system that collects data from the fab, especially during manufacturing ramp ups, and helps engineers find ways to improve yield.

Organisational Performance: the degree to which the organization, with some informational, financial, and human resources, positions itself effectively on the business market. The ability of an organization to reach its goals and optimize results.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Introduction

This chapter focused on the review of studies related to the variables of the study. This chapter discussed the concepts of the study, also reviewed several empirical studies, and presented the theoretical framework upon which the study rests.

2.2 Concept of IT and Performance of Organisations

In the 1960's and 70's, information technology was widely employed by many firms mainly for achieving routine clerical and administrative activities such as processing data related to bookkeeping and accounting activities (Bird & Lehrman, 1993). It was used as a monitor of the firm's internal and external environment; in other words, as a support factor for the other organisational system components (Bili & Raymond, 1993). However, the cost, the distribution, and the fact that it was generally applied to only simple tasks in its early stages discouraged its application to strategic uses in areas such as enhancing the organisation's position against competitors, moving into new markets, and providing managers with better information for effective decision making. The advancement in the technological field along with other advancements have enhanced the economies of information technology and greatly expanded its applications (Bird & Lehrman, 1993). Today, information technology has become not only a tool to process data and record transactions, but also a competitive weapon that can change an industry's structure. Galliers (1994) suggested that because of the rapid pace of technological advances and the impact of information technology on the changing competitive environment, organisations are forced to critically evaluate their management of information and technology resources in order to achieve their strategic objectives.

One of the strongest pieces of evidence of the impact of IT has been illustrated as coming from the firm level analysis that is confirmed to a number of developed countries (OECD, 2003). Most of these studies use a combination of growth accounting methods and econometric models to

examine samples of industries and firms. For example, (Gretton, 2002), studying firm-level data from the Australian Business Longitudinal Survey, found positive and significant links between the use of IT and growth in both manufacturing and service industry. (Brynjolfsson & Hitt, 2003), investigating US firm-level data, proved that IT has a solid impact on productivity. (Pilat & Wolfl, 2004) examined the role of ICT-producer and key ICT-consumer sectors in explaining overall productivity growth in OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) countries; they found that the impact of ICT-producer sectors is most significant in Finland, Ireland, and Korea whereas ICT-consumer sectors in some countries, remarkably US and Australia, had an impressive growth in the second half of the 1990s. (Hempell, 2004) analyzed comparable panel data of the Dutch and German firms in the service industry and found that ICT capital deepening and innovation have complementary impact on productivity. The Massachusetts Institute of Technology group in 1991 concluded that information technology is the platform on which success can be built but organizational factors are crucial to realizing the benefits of automation and 'informating' process (Morton, 1991; Zuboff, 1988). Information technology can be considered to be a series of innovations. Even though the innovations provide organisation with new and different ways of solving problems and enhancing performance, there is still a great deal of research to be done and discussion among researchers and organisational theorists on how innovations should be implemented and managed and how they affect organisations on different levels. It is widely accepted among many authors and researchers in the organisational field that information technology has a significant effect on the performance of the organisation's activities (Bhattacharjee & Hirschheim, 1997; Morris & Westbrook, 1996; Porter & Millar, 1985). For example, information technology applications can be used to improve the level of efficiency of administrative functions in an organisation and to enhance the effectiveness of managerial activities. These applications also can be used as tools to impose better organisation on tasks and to provide better information to managers. Zuboff (1988) pointed out that information technology applications are strongly altering the way in which production operations are carried out in a

variety of industries and thus using information technology to create and acquire a competitive advantage.

Information technology supports the primary objective of organizational performance which is to ensure uninterrupted business operations, delivery of agreed services, cost efficiency and operations quality efficiency (Davenport, 2013). Information technologies can provide powerful strategic and tactical tools for organizations, which, if properly applied and used, could bring great advantages in promoting and strengthening their competitiveness. The proliferation of the internet, as a mainstream communication media and as an infrastructure for business transactions has generated a wide range of strategic implications for businesses in general as well as for the service industries in particular (Christensen, 2002).

Information technology can be used not only for operational purposes but also for tactical and strategic management of hospitality firms. This empowers tourism and hospitality enterprises to communicate directly and more efficiently with prospective customers and suppliers as well as to achieve competitive advantage (Aaker, 2012). It is very important to keep improving IT within an organization to ensure the benefits of better processes, therefore, improving the operations. With improvements in operations come numerous benefits, some of which are; increased service availability to customers, improved return on investment, and simplified and efficient work environments therefore increasing productivity.

Information technology and management information systems are today part of critical components of the institution's overall strategy; they support management's ability to perform reviews. It should be used to recognize aspects, monitor, measure, limit risks, and manage operational performance. Efficient and useable IT should be both operational and informational. As such, management can use IT to measure performance, allocate, manage and control resources, and help an institution comply with regulatory requirements (Yusuf, 2013).

Information technology is a general term that describes any technology that helps to produce, manipulate, store, communicate and disseminate information. There are two parts to information

technology; computer technology and communication technology. Information and communication technology is used as an extended synonym for the term information technology, the term comprises unified communication, their integration to telecommunication networks, computers and enterprise software, middleware, storage and audio-visual systems, which enable users to access, store, transmit, and manipulate information (Mpofu & Watkins-Mathys, 2011). The key concept in information technology that necessitates the study includes; capability, communication and collaboration, modelling and exploration and impact on business functions. The term information technology has expanded to include the role of IT tools not just inside the company but outside the company, for example, Archibugi and Coco (2005), claimed that IT is considered a tool of marketing and contacting customers and looking for possible customers, as well as presenting IT services is distinguished as a potential service for customers (Werthner & Klein, 1999). According to Shirazi, Farid, Gholami and Dolores (2008), IT is also considered as a key enabler for globalization, facilitating worldwide flows of information, capital, ideas, people and products. Some researchers have tried to combine the previous definition by considering IT as a group of elements (hardware, software, and people) that should be working together in the process to present the benefits to the organization in the form of information, product or services (Christensen, 2002; Doganis, 2002; Werthner and Klein, 1999). Laudon (2011) asserts that IT includes all the technology that facilitates the processing, transfer and exchange of information and communication services. It is considered as a subject of expertise that links information technology (computers and applications) and telecommunication networks (intranet and internet), which lets people and computers interrelate irrespective of physical location. Werthner and Klein (1999) conclude that the IT term contains hardware, software, networks and people that should be integrated as one unit by linking each one to the other in a clear process to generate the information that helps the decision-makers, producing products and services presenting, promotion, controlling and for achieving the organization's aims and goals. Information and communication technology is clearly considered a key growth area in this century, specifically, in a dynamic

business and highly competitive environment which requires utilizing advanced IT to improve efficiency, cost effectiveness, and to present high-quality goods and services to customers (Laudon, 2011).

2.3 Organizational Performance

Organizational performance is measured for different levels of hierarchy and can be assessed for individuals, groups, and the entire organization as a whole (Knies, Jacobsen and Tummers, 2016). One of the clearest definitions of Organizational performance describes it in terms of the growth and survival of the firm (Etzioni, 1960; Chandler and Hanks, 1993). In this definition, a firm may consider its performance to be effective if it is able to meet its prescribed goals and continue to improve.

With the advent of technological advancement, it is undeniable that IT will enable organizations to make their business profitable as it has become a major tool in dealing with the many business functions, operations and development of new and innovative products and services. According to recent trends and practices, information technology has become a major consideration for many businesses specifically in dealing with business processes and functions, operational activities, as well as developing and innovating products and services. Recently, about half of the companies operating globally were able to spend 50% of their capital expenditures and investments focused on IT or ICT expecting that large returns will be obtained from such investments. However, many organizations are still lagging behind on how efficiently and effectively they invest their funds into IT investments that serve as critical with the advent of technological advancement it is undeniable that IT will enable organizations to make their business profitable as it has become a major tool in dealing with the many business functions, operations and development of new and innovative products and services. According to recent trends and practices, information technology has become a major consideration for many businesses specifically in dealing with business processes and functions, operational activities, as well as developing and innovating

products and services. Recently, about half of the companies operating globally were able to spend 50% of their capital expenditures and investments are focused on IT or ICT expecting that large returns will be obtained from such investment. However, many organizations are still lagging behind on how efficiently and effectively they invest their funds into IT investments that serve as critical.

With the advent of technological advancement, it is undeniable that IT will enable organizations to make their business profitable as it has become a major tool in dealing with the many business functions, operations and development of new and innovative products and services. According to the recent trends and practices, information technology has become a major consideration for many businesses specifically in dealing with business processes and functions, operational activities, as well as developing and innovating products and services. Recently, about half of the companies operating globally were able to spend 50% of their capital expenditures and investments are focused on IT or ICT expecting that large returns will be obtained from such investments. However, many organizations are still lagging behind on how efficiently and effectively they invest their funds into IT investments that serve as critical deciding factors for companies to pursue and considering the lack of experts who will manage the investments which is precisely the reason why many firms fail as they fail to link IT to business opportunities and profitable endeavors using the IT-based investment.

Several authors and researchers have examined the impacts and or influence of IT use on an organization's performance whether products or services and found a positive relationship between these two main variables (Beckey, Elliot, & Procket, 1996; McNutt, & Boland, 1999). Accordingly, results also affirmed the relationship by offering recommendations that IT has indeed played a significant role in the improvement of providing both the quality and quantity of relevant information for decision makings for managers and businesses as well as a baseline for product and service innovations (Mano, 2009). Many companies set aside their budget and

resources in accordance with their goals and objectives by maximizing the use of their resources on investing

into IT and have been proven through this research to perform better in their workplaces than those that set less investment on IT (McAfee & Brynjolfsson, 2008). In other words, achieving higher performance requires considerable and good IT infrastructure with good management practices in IT utilization (Mwania & Muganda, 2012).

2.4 The Hospitality Industry in Nigeria

The hospitality industry in Nigeria is enormous. This is buttressed by the fact that Nigerians naturally engage in leisure activities and generally are fun-loving people. The boom in the entertainment industry is also responsible for the demand for facilities that promote business and pleasure; hence the boom experienced investing in the hospitality sector. Nigeria is expected to be the fastest-growing hospitality market with a projected 12 per cent compound annual increase from 2019 to 2023 according to a PricewaterhouseCoopers PwC projection.

An investigation by Tribune newspaper (March 17, 2023) shows that globally, the tourism industry contributes about 10 per cent to the global GDP. This is expected to rise in four years with significant upward movement in Mauritius, Kenya, Nigeria, and South Africa. In Nigeria, the contribution of travel and tourism to the nation's GDP was 5.1 per cent in 2019. In 2020 however, the upward trajectory slowed down due to the Coronavirus pandemic.

It contributed 3.6 per cent to Nigeria's GDP in 2021, which was equal to around 16 billion U.S. dollars. The World Travel and Tourism Council's (WTTC) Economic Impact Report (EIR), however, in 2022, revealed that Nigeria's travel and tourism sector's contribution to GDP was forecast to grow at an average rate of 5.4 per cent between 2022 and 2032. According to Statista Research, in 2021, there were more than 2.4 million jobs in the travel and tourism sector in Nigeria. The sector is expected to scale up Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and create an average of 2.6 million employment opportunities yearly for the next decade.

According to the WTTC's EIR, "The Travel and Tourism sector in Nigeria is expected to create 2.6 million new jobs over the next decade, doubling the number of those employed within the sector by 2032." The WTTC's forecast shows that an average of nearly 260,000 new jobs would be created every year for the next 10 years, reaching more than 5.1 million.

Despite the decrease compared to 2019 due to the pandemic, travel and tourism accounted for nearly five per cent of total employment in the country by 2021. These statistics only show the potential within the industry. An increase in investments in the sector will only continue if specific issues raised by stakeholders are addressed. Despite the positive indices within the tourism and hospitality industry, the absence of quality service delivery has remained an issue. In the travel sector, bottlenecks to tourism growth include lack of internal airline connectivity, poor road network, poor marketing, lack of institutional coordination, limited skills and experience, lack of domestic tourism promotion, unfriendly visa policy, and importantly, limited ICT usage, among others.

Finally, the low levels of IT presence and utilization are also a big challenge, this is because the tourist circuit areas are not covered with the essential infrastructure necessary for IT technologies to thrive, these are; the mobile telephone network, the internet, radio and television networks. This factor makes the destination unfavorable to tourists from developed countries (Kim, Eves & Scales, 2013). Hospitality organizations are turning to performance measurement and management in order to qualify for the International Organization for Standardization standard certifications and Company of the Year Awards. General business pressures, the achievement of the coveted five-star rating and membership in international hotel associations have created the need for effective key performance indicators. Furthermore, organizations that have already implemented a performance measurement system have shown much better results (Njenga & Alexander, 2012).

Been outside of one's home and are paying for staying then the all the services used during the stay and broadly within or related to or provided by the place of stay comes under hospitality industry.

Hospitality means welcoming a guest and making them comfortable at your place by looking after their needs during their temporary stay. When firm do and provide the above things as a service, business to anyone, with the help of products and services, for a price it becomes hospitality industry.

Hospitality industry can be defined and understood as an industry which provides facility for stay, food and complete related services for the comfort and leisure of the travelers and visitors.

Hospitality is the industry covering all the products and services that serve travelers, tourists and all types of visitors. knowing tourism implies understanding hospitality industry. Within services the hospitality industry means offering all the paid services to visitors or travelers for their stay including more services to make their stay more comfortable.

The hospitality industry means providing services such as stay, lodging, food, drinks, entertainment and more related services of facilities that a traveler or tourist may need or which can be of their help and comfort. It is basically offering all the possible facilities, comfort and related services to all those people who are visiting that place for some period of time mainly as tourists or travelers.

The industry of hospitality mainly covers accommodation, hotels, motels, restaurants, bread & breakfast. This hospitality industry mainly caters to tourists and travelers. These tourists or travelers can be from other countries, other cities and even can be local.

This industry is closely associated and a part of the tourism industry. it is a key part of the tourism industry value chain. This industry is mainly driven by growing tourism, yet it caters to both tourists and travelers. Hospitality and Tourism industry are closely related and each plays an important role in development and growth of the other industry. Tourism brings revenue, growth and development for hospitality. On the other hand, hospitality industry adds to the overall value

and importance of tourism. It creates more tourism demand, makes it look more attractive, adds the much-needed comfort level for tourists and travelers. Without hospitality tourism would be incomplete and will not achieve the growth.

2.4.1 Hotel Reservation Systems

A hotel reservation system, commonly known as a central reservation system (CRS) is a computerized system that stores and distributes information of a hotel, resort or other lodging facilities. A CRS offers assistance to hoteliers to manage all of their online marketing and sales where they can upload their rates and service availabilities to be seen by sales channels (www.ijiset.com). The list of main modules that are present in a CRS are: Content, Information stored on a CRS and Reporting. Content consists of Reservations, Profiles, Groups and Blocks, Rate and Inventory Control, Administration, Global Distribution Interface, Web-based Interface. Information commonly stored in a CRS consists of Room Types, Rate plans architecture, Room rates and conditions (guarantee, deposit, customized cancellation rules, minimum length of stay, maximum length of stay, closed to arrival, arrival not allowed, departure not allowed, ...), Room inventories, Generic hotel information (address, phone number, fax number), Reservation information. The CRS Reporting module provides a number of standards reports. System reports may be generated automatically and may be run daily, weekly, monthly, yearly. It includes Expected Arrivals, Reservation, Property Forecast, Total Booking Activity, Stay Activity, Monthly Booking Activity, Daily Booking Activity and Property Detail.

2.4.2 Property Management Systems

Property management system (PMS) also known as Property Automation System (PAS) refers to a computer-based control system that needs to be installed within properties to monitor and regulate the property's electrical and mechanical equipment such as power system, lighting, and ventilation to confirm sustainability. Given that the systems connected to a PMS usually represent a property's energy use of 40%, this percentage will approach 70% in case lighting is included. It

is essential for a PMS to be set up because they are critical elements to intelligently manage the energy demand, for example, electrical system, plumbing, fire alarm system, heating ventilation and air-conditioning (HVAC), electric power control, and illumination control. As a result, through PMS, property management requires to have electronic centralized regulation of a property's air-conditioning, ventilation and heating, lighting, and other property systems. Bearing in mind enhanced utilities' life cycle, decrease in energy operating costs and consumption, property systems' efficient operation, and comfort of the occupant, the PMS objectives require to be enhanced. Consequently, distributed control system's great work on the computer networking of automation instruments should be structured to control and monitor the HVAC and humidity ventilation, control systems, lighting, flood and fire safety, security, and mechanical systems within a property. Therefore, the core functionality of a PAS should be retained within the property climate in a specified range, offer malfunction alarms to the maintenance staff of a property, monitor device failure and performance in all property systems, and lighting to rooms based on an occupancy schedule. Compared to uncontrolled properties, a PAS reduces property energy and costs of maintenance, hence most industrial, institutional, and commercial properties constructed after 2000 include a PMS that should be restructured for a timeworn property. Normally, several timeworn properties have been retrofitted with a novel PAS, financed via insurance and energy savings, as well as other savings linked with fault detection and preemptive maintenance. So, it is regarded that a property regulated by a PMS is frequently termed as an intelligent property, a "smart home" in case of residence or just a "smart property." When proprietary procedures were used in homes, industrial and commercial properties must have in history depended on healthy recognized procedures such as BACnet. Current IEEE standards and groups' efforts have offered a standard-based grounds for different networking of several instruments in several physical networks for varied purposes and service quality and failover, which promises proper support to human safety and health.

Designing property to accommodate a PAS for energy, water, and air preservation characteristics, as well as appropriate electrical instrument demand response in a typical PAS function, is necessary. This is due to the fact that it is the more refined ventilation and moisture monitoring needed of “tight” insulation for achieving environmental sustainability.

2.4.3 Yield Management Systems

This is the process of allocating the right type of capacity to the right kind of customer at the right price so as to maximize revenue or yield. In the case of hotels, yield management is concerned with the number of rooms that should be sold at various rate levels. Obviously, a tradeoff exists. The manager would prefer to sell all rooms at the highest rate possible, but since this rarely is feasible, following this policy may lead to empty rooms and lost revenue. Conversely, if a hotel fills its rooms with low-price customers, the revenue that could have been obtained from higher rates will be lost. The objective of yield management, then, is to define what these trade-offs should be. How many rooms should be allocated to and protected for each market segment over time? Or kinl defined the yield statistic as the occupancy rate multiplied by the rate efficiency. The rate efficiency is the average room rate divided by the maximum room rate. As he points out, hotel managers need to be concerned with maximizing yield, or revenue, rather than focusing only on a high occupancy rate or a high average room rate. Another definition of yield management, borrowed from the airline industry, is maximizing revenue (or yield) per available room. This may be a more appropriate definition because of the difficulty in defining the maximum room rate. Yield management consists of two separate but related parts: room-inventory management and pricing. The inventory-management process deals with how different types of rooms are to be allocated to demand. The pricing procedure is more concerned with the best prices to charge in different situations. In this article, I will concentrate primarily on the room- inventory component of yield management.

The airline industry is considered the birthplace of yield management. After deregulation in the late 1970s, airline competition increased, and the airlines tried to operate their planes as efficiently

as possible. Yield management was one of the methods developed as a way of increasing competitive advantage and increasing revenue. In airlines, yield management is concerned with selling the right seat to the right customer at the right price so as to maximize yield. The airline and hotel industries have several characteristics in common that make them ideal candidates for yield-management systems. Both have relatively fixed capacities. Once an airplane has been purchased or a hotel has been built, it is rather difficult and expensive to increase capacity. The idea, then, is to use your capacity in the best (most profitable) way possible. Yield-management techniques are appropriate when a firm is operating with a relatively fixed capacity, when demand can be segmented into clearly identified partitions, when inventory is perishable, when the product is sold well in advance, when demand fluctuates substantially, and when marginal sales costs are low but marginal production costs are high.

2.4.4 The Use of Search engine optimization (SEO)

A search engine is a tool used to find, analyze and retrieve information from the World Wide Web. It can access website pages and present information from the site to the user searching online. Some search engines mine data, use algorithms or human input to identify websites. As a result, the large amounts of data online do not always present the user with the necessary “hits” they may be seeking so search engine optimization (SEO) is a tool used by website creators for making search engines identifies the type of information they may contain which will be more useful for users matching similar interests. For example, a hotel in London can optimize their website with relevant keywords, links with other sites and other relevant categories to be identified by a search engine such as Google or Yahoo Search. So, when someone is using Google and looking for hotels in London, that web search will match more accordingly with hotels in London rather than providing endless lists of hotels from all other irrelevant destinations. SEO can lead to greater sales and leads, long term growth in visitors to the site and less marketing effort required.

2.4.5 Social Media and Internet Marketing

The Internet is an example of a networked technology which interconnects with other forms of ICT and its use is not exclusive. There is a large degree of overlap with other areas of ICT and interconnections with the general sphere of marketing a destination. Destination Management Organisations (e.g. Visit England) are responsible for promoting tourism and hospitality services for a specific location and may operate their own Destination Management Systems (DMS) for collecting, disseminating and promoting services in a certain area. SMEs can use their sites and systems to integrate with local DMS for reservations, providing information and general marketing (WTO, 2011). Buhalis and Licata (2002) note the modern integration of other organisations and service providers in modern eTourism and also identified the consolidation of existing technologies such as GDS and CRS serving the existing distribution model with travel operators and agents, but they also identified the new 'eMediaries' assisting ecommerce; this being the internet, interactive digital TV, mobile devices and mobile commerce ('mCommerce') as demonstrated in figure 3. Social media plays an increasing role in modern eTourism and the interaction between stakeholders in the industry social media is defined as being an online platform and technology used by people to share their opinions and experiences. Social media can also include photos, videos, music and opinions expressed by contributors. This for example means consumers can promote certain hotels or destinations when they have had an experience and this can affect the image perceived by future consumers. Social media is a powerful democratic force expressing social opinion and can enable communication and collaboration significantly. Integration of websites, ICT systems with the social network can lead to future commercial potential and also run the risk of bad promotion or adverse media reaching a wider audience so must be considered by businesses before developing marketing campaigns. However, SMEs do have resource constraints limiting their ability to adopt ICT and integrate with modern social technologies compared to larger organisations (Kuttainen and Lexhagen, 2011).

2.5 Review of Empirical Studies

A study by Ayatse (2012) investigated the impact of information communication technology (ICT) on corporate performance. The result of the study show that ICT has positively contributed to cooperated performance. Pirzada and Ahmed (2013) study the effect of new technology on firm business objective. The result of the study indicate that new technologies have a strong relationship with firm business objective. Hawajreh and Sharabati (2012) investigated the impact of information technology on knowledge management practice in Jordan. The result of the study shows that there is positive and significant relationship between information technology and knowledge management practice. (Onu et al., 2015) examined the effect of information communication technology investment on organizational productivity and growth of small and medium scale enterprises in developing countries. The result of the study shows that positive and significant effect exists between independent variable and dependent variable of the study.

Gronroos, C. (2000) Identified the role of ICT in service delivery as providing systems for effective internal service support from support persons and systems, and other systems and technologies that make it possible for the contact employees to give good service. If such support is lacking, even the most customer-orientated and service-minded employees will eventually start to feel frustrated and lose interest in being good part-time marketers. Gronroos, C. (2000) used for “the people representing the firm (who) create value for the customers in various service processes,

“Part-time marketing” following Gummesson, (1991) definition is the term Gronroos, (2000) used for the people representing the firm (who) create value for the customers in various service processes, such as deliveries, customer training, claims handling, service and maintenance etc, and some are directly engaged in sales and cross-sales. Thus, they are involved in marketing” (p. 56) without being part of the formal marketing effort of the firm. Both writers emphasis’ the

forming the customers' image of the firm. A number of writers address various points of interaction between people, technology and service delivery in hotels.

Choi and Kimes (2002) Examined booking systems in hotels and presented an overview of some of the internal technology as the following discussion outlines. For each individual hotel, the Property Management System (PMS) is at the centre of both technology and hotel operations.

This system is used to manage the room inventory, record guest details and produce billing information. It often interfaces with other systems such as the telephone systems and food and beverage point of sales terminals to allow integrated billing and management reporting. For hotels that are part of a chain or franchise group there may be a Central Reservation System (CRS). This allows on-booking between 10 hotels as well as the acceptance of direct bookings from a Central Reservation Office (CRO). These systems commonly have direct access into the PMS and update automatically so the hotel front desk and Central Reservations Office have the same view of the hotel's available room inventory. Outside of hotels exists the Global Distribution Systems (GDS) such as Sabre and Galileo. These systems include not only hotels but airlines, car rental and other travel resources and are commonly used by professional travel agents. In many cases these are allocated a block of rooms within the hotels PMS systems but bookings from the GDS do not automatically update the PMS and must be entered manually. Bookings from the Internet can enter the system through any of these marketing channels, either via an on-line travel agent or directly from the customer. Choi, S., & Kimes, S. E. (2002) Noted that each of these channels has different costs associated with them for the hotel. GDS in particular incurs a charge for being listed, as well as substantial commissions per transaction. However, in their computer simulation of revenue contributions for a business hotel, no significant difference was found between revenue management by length of stay and room rate compared to adding the distribution channel to the process. They did note that the gap between room rates in comparison to the channel fees would be likely to affect the outcome. For example, in hotels where there was very little difference

between room rate levels with widely varying distribution costs, the hotel would need to include distribution costs in their revenue management model.

In a similar study of small-scale properties in Scotland, Buick (2003) found that even among hotels that did not have a computer, most had a web page to advertise and promote their business. Again, many of these properties used their computer for accounting and word processing. There was limited use of PMS type packages but extensive use of spreadsheets which individual owners could use to build functionality specific to their business needs. Of the sites not using a computer, (30% of the sample), the reasons most commonly given were that the owner did not see a requirement for one to operate the business and that the capital costs associated were too high.

Brotherton, and Turner (2001) Considered the implementation of a Computerized Yield Management System (CYMS) in a large hotel. For this case study, they interviewed a number of the managers and staff about the training they received and how they understood the system to work. They found a level of confusion as to who was finally responsible for the system and, in the response of the front-line staff, whose interactions with the guest in the booking process should be influenced by the system. Particularly worrying was that the Reception Manager reported that they were “committed to it (Yield Management) but none of my staff are” (p. 39).

Hailu (2014) determine the impact of information system (IS) on organizational performance with reference to ethio-telecom Southern region, Hawassa, Ethiopia. The result of the study shows that top management commitment facilities, skilled man power, information ethic, quality system, user perception, significantly affect organizational performance. Another similar empirical study show that information and communication technology have significant positive effect in innovation activities of companies Penalba (2015). Similar study by Alabar and Agema (2014) indicated that the information and communication technology have significant influence on customer

satisfaction. Sepehrdoust and Khodae (2013) found positive and significant effect between ICT and employment selected of Selected OIC Countries.

Olise et al. (2014) investigated the determinant of ICT adoption for Improve SMEs performance in Anambra state Nigeria. The result indicated that there is positive and significant relationship between dimension and SMEs performance. Binuya and Aregbehola (2004) findings of the study indicated that the use of ICT increased return on capital employed as well as return on asset of south African banking industry and the study discover more of the contribution come from ICT cost efficiency.

2.6 Theoretical Framework

Many theoretical frameworks have sought to explain IT's impact on organizational performance. An early example is Porter and Millar's (1985) seminal work on the value chain, where information has the ability to provide value in each link of a firm's value chain. An especially pervasive theoretical framework is the resource-based view (RBV) of the firm, which holds that a resource must meet four criteria in order to create value: 1. valuable; 2. rare; 3. hard to copy; and 4. non-substitutable (Wernerfelt, 1984; Barney, 1991). Organizations are amalgams of physical, human and knowledge resources that confer competitive advantage to the firm that can control and leverage the unique characteristics of the resource (Melville et al., 2004). In contrast, Carr (2003) critically questions the value IT is able to confer to the firm, precisely because IT resources have become commoditized and are therefore no longer rare or hard to imitate. Certainly, some IT assets are not difficult to duplicate, such as infrastructure and networking components; however, resources alone do not explain the difference of firm's competitiveness. Teece's (1997) dynamic capabilities theory effectively addresses this issue. The dynamic capabilities theory extends the RBV, but emphasizes capabilities instead of merely assets as the source of competitive advantage: Winners in the global marketplace have been firms that can demonstrate timely responsiveness and rapid and flexible product innovation, coupled with the management capability to effectively coordinate and redeploy internal and external competences

(Teece et al., 1997). In other words, firms cannot rely on procuring IT infrastructure as a necessary condition for sustained competitive advantage, but must also possess and nurture internal capabilities to manage that infrastructure effectively. The RBV remains the dominant theoretical explanation of IT business value as evidenced by Melville et al.'s (2004) comprehensive literature review. They found two main formulations of performance:

1. efficiency; and
2. effectiveness.

Their overall framework was supported by the RBV with IT and complementary organizational resources supporting business processes that lead to organizational performance (Melville et al., 2004). Similarly, Piccoli and Ives's (2005) literature review of how IT-dependent strategic initiatives lead to sustained competitive advantage uses the RBV with elements of dynamic capabilities theory. The framework identifies four barriers to the erosion of sustained competitive advantage:

1. IT resources;
2. complementary resources;
3. IT projects; and
4. pre-emption coupled with two dynamic capabilities which reinforce these four barriers:
 - organizational learning; and
 - asset stock accumulation (Piccoli and Ives, 2005).

Kohli and Devaraj's (2003) meta-analysis of IS literature on structural variables of IT payoff studies between 1990 and 2000 found empirical support for a number of propositions. IT payoff studies differ depending on the industry sector, sample size, data source, and type of dependent variable (Kohli and Devaraj, 2003). In addition, the authors provide a useful conception of IT impact for our meta-analysis by categorizing dependent variables as either “profitability” and “productivity”. A different but related stream of research on IT value focuses on the DeLone and McLean (1992) theoretical framework of IS success. IS success is comprised of many dimensions,

including system quality, information quality, use, and user satisfaction which lead to individual impact and ultimately organizational impact (Delone and McLean, 1992). This framework was later extended to include service quality as a fifth form of IS success and organizational impact was broadened to include “net benefits” as an outcome (Delone and McLean, 2003). However, a more recent review of IS success model literature indicated that the dimension of service quality received no attention in 34 journals from 2003 to 2007 (Urbach et al., 2008). The dominant paradigm of recent IS success research focuses on user evaluations via surveys regarding the impact of a particular information system resulting in a structural equation model (Urbach et al., 2009). There does not seem to be any more skepticism since Carr (2003) that IT does, in fact, provide firm-level value or since Brynjolfsson (2000) that there is any more productivity paradox (Kohli and Devaraj, 2003). However, the empirical studies in IS literature on what that value is and how it is to be measured remains fragmented. There is no consistent set of performance measures. Conducting a meta-analysis of the literature is a useful means of critically examining disparate findings (Wolf, 1986) and furthermore, meta-analysis of IS literature is necessary to bolster the cumulative tradition of the discipline (Hwang, 1996).

2.7 Conceptual Framework

In this framework, there are certain factors influencing information technology in the hospitality industry. For this study, three factors are considered as the independent variables i.e., HRS, PMS and YMS. Organisational Performance (OP) of the hospitality industry is the dependent variable that is affected by the independent variables as shown below.

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter gives the methodology that was used to accomplish the already established research objectives and questions. It looks at the study's; research design, target population, instrument validity and reliability test, data collection, and data analysis discussed.

3.2 Research Design

The study adopted descriptive survey design. According to Mugenda and Mugenda, (2003) and Siedlecki (2020), descriptive research design is a sort of research design that tries to systematically gather data to characterize a phenomenon, circumstance, or population that is being examined. Kothari (2004) stated that "Descriptive research includes surveys and fact-finding enquiries of different kinds". The major purpose of descriptive research is description of state of affairs as it exists at present. The researcher made an interpretation of the data with using descriptive study. The design chosen for this study due to its ability to ensure minimization of bias and maximization of reliability of evidence collected.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population consisted of general managers and IT staff in 100 starred hotels in Nigeria. Therefore, population of the study is 200 staff.

Table 3.1: *Sample Frame and Sample Size*

Hotel Rating (Class)	Number
5 Star	5
4 Star	15
3 Star	25
2 Star	35
1 Star	40
Total	100

3.4 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Since the data collected was in quantitative form, the study adopted quantitative methods of data analysis. Census sampling technique was used and all the population of the study.

3.5 Research Model

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + E$$

Where Y = Dependent variable

X₁, X₂, X₃ = Independent variables

a = Constant

b₁ b₂ b₃ = Coefficient

E = Error term

3.5 Method of Data Collection

Primary data was used in this study. Primary data was gathered using structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A constituted of the background general information, while section B dealt with the Influence of information technology on operational performance of firms in the Nigerian hospitality industry. Respondents were required to rate their responses using a Likert scale designed questionnaire. This design enabled the researcher to capture the positive and negative attributes from the respondents. The questionnaires were

administered through emails. Telephone calls were also used for clarification on some questions and probing. The respondents included general managers and IT staff; the study collected primary data. Primary data was collected from respondents using an anonymously filled questionnaire distributed to respondents by providing access to the online survey form by sending out notification emails. The results were available online immediately after every respondent had finished answering the questions.

3.6 Method of Data Analysis

The collected data was edited, coded and entered for analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (Version 22.0) computer package. Both preliminary and inferential statistics were used. Factor analysis sorted the eight factors into three main factor components according to their absolute values. The higher the absolute value of the loading, the more the explanatory power of the variable.

The statistical package for (SPSS) version 22.0 was used for the preliminary analysis. All the questionnaires from the respondents were properly and carefully scrutinized so as to check on the omissions, completeness and inconsistencies upon which coding was done. The study's hypothesized relationships were subjected to analysis using a Structural Equation Model (SEM).

3.7 Validity and Reliability of Instrument

The reliability and validity of an instrument is the extent to which the instrument is able to precisely measure what it was designed to measure using composite reliability, content and construct validity (i.e., convergent and discriminant validity). A number of steps were taken by the researcher to make the instruments valid. Face-value validity of the questionnaire was assumed through comments from the supervising lecturer. Finally, the constructive criticism, advice and suggestions of the supervisor were seriously considered to ensure the validity of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was assessed using composite reliability while the validity of the instrument was determined using discriminant and convergent validity.

CHAPTER FOUR DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter is dedicated to conducting a comprehensive examination of the data gathered from respondents. The initial phase of analysis involved a series of assessments, which included evaluating the response rate, identifying any missing values, detecting outliers, assessing multicollinearity, examining the potential for common method bias, considering the impact of non-response bias, and conducting tests to assess the normality of the data distribution. These preliminary analyses were carried out using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Subsequently, the study's hypothesized relationships were subjected to analysis using a Structural Equation Model (SEM). This meticulous and all-encompassing analytical approach ensures a robust evaluation of the data and establishes a solid foundation for subsequent statistical modeling.

4.2 Response Rate

In this study, a total of 200 questionnaires were distributed among Hospitality firms in Lagos State, Nigeria. Impressively, a substantial 94.5% (189 out of 200) of the initially distributed questionnaires were diligently completed and returned. The credit for this high response rate goes to the researcher's conscientious efforts in ensuring prompt questionnaire completion and return by the respondents. Only 8 out of the 200 surveys (4.0%) were returned incomplete by a few respondents, and these were subsequently excluded from the analysis. As indicated in Table 4.1, 181 questionnaires (90.5%) were fully completed and returned, while 11 questionnaires (5.5%) were not returned.

It is worth noting that Malhotra and Grover (1998) have recommended that a valid response rate exceeding the 50% threshold is necessary for establishing credible generalizations. In this context, the study's exceptionally high valid response rate of 94.5% not only surpasses this

threshold but also underscores the robustness of the collected data. This high response rate lends credibility to the study's findings, ensuring a strong basis for reliable generalizations and meaningful conclusions.

Table 4.1: *Questionnaire Distribution and Response Rate*

Questionnaire	Frequency	Rate%
Distributed Questionnaires	200	100
Unreturned/Not Responded	11	5.5
Returned Ruestionnaires	189	94.5
Rejected/Removed	8	4.0
Retained/Usable	181	90.5

4.3 Preliminary analysis

Following the guidance of Tabachnick and Fidell (2012), a preliminary analysis was conducted to ensure the data's integrity and accuracy. The data were initially coded using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). For instance, the four items assessing the hotel reservation system were coded as HRS1, HRS2, HRS3, and HRS4. Similarly, the property management system was represented by four items: PMS1, PMS2, PMS3, and PMS4. The four items evaluating the yield management system were coded as YMS1, YMS2, YMS3, and YMS4, while the three items measuring organizational performance were labeled as OP1, OP2, and OP3.

In the second phase of the preliminary analysis, the aim was to identify missing values within the dataset. It was observed that, unlike the property management system and organizational performance, which had relatively few missing values of four each, the yield management system exhibited seven missing values, and the hotel reservation system had ten missing values (as indicated in Table 4.2). To address this issue, Tabachnick and Fidell's (2012) recommendation of mean replacement was applied, considering that the extent of missing data

was moderate. This approach helps to minimize the impact of missing values on the analysis while maintaining the dataset's integrity for subsequent analysis.

Table 4.2 *Total and Percentage of Missing Values*

Latent Variables	Number of Missing Values
Hotel Reservation System	10
Organisational Performance	4
Property Management System	4
Yield Management System	7
Total	25 out of 2,715 data points
Percentage	0.92

Note: The total number of randomly missing values for the complete data set is divided by the total number of data points multiplied by 100 to determine the percentage of missing values.

4.4 Outliers

An outlier, often referred to as an anomaly, is an observation that deviates significantly from the typical pattern due to unique characteristics or features, as explained by Hair, Black, Babin, and Anderson (2010). In multivariate analysis, the most effective method for detecting outliers is through the use of Mahalanobis distance (D^2). In this study, the search for outliers was carried out utilizing multiple linear regression in SPSS. A newly generated response number (e.g., data set serial number) was set as the dependent variable (DV), while all measurement items, except for demographic characteristics, served as independent variables (IVs). This analysis resulted in the creation of a new variable named MAH_1, representing the Mahalanobis distance (D^2) for the selected set of independent variables. Subsequently, this newly generated variable was organized in columns and sorted in ascending order based on their values. The chi-square distribution was then examined using the same number of degrees of freedom as the Mahalanobis distance (D^2). Given that the dataset contained a total of 15 items across all variables, the computation of the Mahalanobis distance (D^2) involved summing all these variables, corresponding to the degrees of freedom. The right-tail p-value of the chi-square distribution was calculated using the Mahalanobis distance (D^2) with the same degrees of freedom. Following Field's (2017) recommendation, a stringent significance level of < 0.001

was applied to identify outliers. As a result of this rigorous investigation, no outliers with significance levels below 0.001 were detected.

4.5 Normality test

The foundation of multivariate analysis hinges upon the assumption of normality, which not only specifies the shape of a metric variable's data distribution but also its relationship with the normal distribution, as highlighted by Hair, Page, and Brunsveld (2020). Deviations from normality can jeopardize the validity of subsequent statistical tests. However, previous research has indicated that Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) can perform effectively even with non-normally distributed data. Nonetheless, Hair et al. (2019) proposed that highly skewed data may increase bootstrap standard errors, potentially leading to an underestimation of the statistical significance of path coefficients. Therefore, they recommended that researchers assess data distribution to ensure its suitability for PLS-SEM analysis.

In this study, an assessment of multivariate normality was conducted using a graphical technique, aligning with the guidance provided by Field (2017). Field (2017) suggests that when dealing with a large sample size of 100 or more respondents, it is more critical to visually inspect the shape of the distribution rather than merely looking at skewness and kurtosis values. To ascertain normality assumptions, the study utilized a histogram and probability plots, as recommended by Field. The histogram presented in Figure 4.1 displayed bars that closely aligned with a normal curve, indicating that the data collected for this research adhered to a normal distribution pattern. Therefore, it can be asserted that the study's data met the normality assumptions, with the graphical approach confirming the normality of the dataset.

Figure 4.1: Normality of Data Using Histogram

4.6 Common method bias

In this study, data for all variables were collected simultaneously through a single instrument, a common practice in cross-sectional surveys. However, it is important to recognize that such an approach has the potential to introduce a common method bias (CMB). As noted by Eichhorn (2014), surveys, being a frequently used instrument in empirical research, can inadvertently bias respondents' responses. Common method bias arises when variations in responses can be attributed to the measurement process rather than the constructs the measurements intend to capture, according to Podsakoff, Mackenzie, Lee, and Podsakoff (2003). Specifically, common method variance (CMV) occurs when responses systematically differ due to the use of similar scaling methods on measurements collected from a single data source.

However, it is worth noting that according to Fuller et al. (2015), common method biases (CMB) occur when the method itself serves as a causative factor and substantially alters the causal relationships among constructs. Kock (2015) points out that common method bias can arise from factors like social desirability and respondents' tendencies to provide consistent or

agreeable responses, as well as their mood, the length of the scale, item ambiguity, and positively framed items. Common method bias, as described by Podsakoff et al. (2003), has the potential to affect the significance, effect size, and direction of coefficients in statistical analyses, making it challenging to ascertain whether the observed relationships accurately reflect reality.

To mitigate the potential impact of common method bias, a procedural approach recommended by scholars like Podsakoff et al. (2003) and Hartmann (2019) was adopted in this study. One such approach involved creating psychological separation between the measurement of the independent variable and the dependent variable, especially when obtaining data from different sources was challenging. This separation helps ensure that the measurement process itself does not lead to artificial relationships between constructs. Additionally, procedural remedies included minimizing construct ambiguity, using clear and concise research questions, and ensuring content validity in scale items.

Several specific procedural techniques were employed in this study to address common method bias. These included avoiding complex terminology and double-barreled questions in the questionnaire, providing clear instructions to respondents, emphasizing the importance of objectivity and honesty in responses, and ensuring the privacy and confidentiality of respondents. Such procedural remedies, as suggested by Fuller et al. (2015) and Podsakoff et al. (2003), have the potential to mitigate the impact of common method bias and ensure the reliability and validity of the study's findings.

4.7 Non-response bias test

Non-response bias, as elucidated by Lambert and Harrington (1989), pertains to differences in responses between individuals who participate in a survey (responders) and those who choose not to (non-respondents). To mitigate this potential bias, the study employed a time-based extrapolation approach initially introduced by Armstrong and Overton (1977). This method

sought to compare early responders (those who replied within 21 days) with late responders (those who responded after 21 days) to estimate the characteristics of non-respondents, under the assumption that non-respondents and late responders might share certain traits. As an additional safeguard against non-response bias, the study adhered to Lindner, Murphy, and Briers' (2001) recommended minimum response rate of 50%, a criterion that this study successfully met. Following Armstrong and Overton's methodology, the study categorized respondents into two groups: early responders (comprising 134 respondents, or 74%) and late responders (consisting of 47 respondents, or 26%). This division resulted in a higher percentage of usable questionnaire responses, as depicted in Table 4.3. To assess the potential presence of non-response bias in variables such as celebrity credibility, celebrity attractiveness, celebrity-product match, brand image, and customer loyalty, an independent sample t-test was conducted, with the detailed results provided in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: *Results of Independent Samples T-Test for Non- Response Bias*

Variables	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	
						F	Sig.
HRS	Early	134	3.246	0.881	0.120	2.532	0.196
	Late	47	3.143	0.871	0.131		
OP	Early	134	3.591	0.334	0.163	2.913	0.143
	Late	47	3.408	0.336	0.154		
PMS	Early	134	3.121	0.368	0.162	2.622	0.182
	Late	47	3.212	0.359	0.155		
YMS	Early	134	3.815	0.324	0.187	3.214	0.112
	Late	47	3.748	0.312	0.199		

In line with Aliyu's (2020) findings presented in Table 4.3, the equality of variance values for all three variables considered in Levene's equality of variance test exceeded the significance

level of 0.05. This outcome suggests that the assumption of equal variances between early and late responders was satisfied in this study. Therefore, it can be reasonably inferred that non-response bias does not exert a significant influence on this research. Furthermore, adhering to the criteria established by Lindner et al. (2001), the study achieved a response rate of 74%, surpassing the 50% threshold. This demonstrates that non-response bias is not a substantial concern, as the collected responses effectively capture a range of characteristics within the research group, thereby permitting the generalization of the study's findings to a broader population.

4.8 Multicollinearity

Multicollinearity, a common issue in statistical analysis, arises when two or more independent variables exhibit high correlations among themselves. This can pose challenges in discerning the individual contributions of these variables in explaining variance in the dependent variable, as well as technical difficulties in estimating a multiple regression model.

To assess the presence of multicollinearity in the study, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was employed as a diagnostic tool. Typically, a VIF value of 3.3 or higher is considered indicative of serious multicollinearity, as suggested by Kock (2015). However, it is noteworthy that in this study, all VIF values presented in Table 4.4 are below the threshold of 4.4. This finding implies that there were no significant issues of multicollinearity among the independent variables, suggesting that the variables included in the regression analysis did not exhibit problematic high correlations with each other. This ensures the reliability of the multiple regression model and the validity of the results.

Table 4.4: *Collinearity diagnostic: Correlation and Variance inflation factor (VIF)*

Constructs	HRS	PMS	YMS	Variance inflation factor (VIF)
Hotel Reservation System	1			2.113
Property Management System		1		2.471
Yield Management System	0.511	0.430	1	2.393

4.9 Assessment of Path Model

The study adopted a Structural Equation Model (SEM) as its analytical framework to scrutinize both the measurement path and the structural path of the model. This method was chosen to thoroughly evaluate the soundness and consistency of the paths in the study, in addition to investigating the postulated relationships among the variables under investigation.

4.9.1 Measurement Model

The measurement model was constructed to assess several critical aspects, including internal consistency, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. Firstly, item loadings were examined, following Hulland's (1999) recommendation to retain items with loadings of 0.5 or higher while discarding those below this threshold. Fortunately, no item was removed due to all loadings above 0.5 threshold. To assess the reliability of the research instrument, composite reliability was calculated, and as per Sekaran and Bougie's (2016) guideline, all values presented in Table 4.5 surpass the 0.7 cutoff, affirming the instrument's reliability and suitability for this investigation. Furthermore, in accordance with the criteria suggested by Fornell and others, the average variance score, as depicted in Table 4.5, consistently exceeds the 0.5 benchmark, thus providing confirmation of the convergent validity of the research instrument.

Figure 4.2: Measurement Model

Table 4.5: Item Loadings, Internal Consistency, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE).

Constructs	Indicators	Loadings	Composite Reliability	AVE
Hotel Reservation System	HRS1	0.673	0.846	0.581
	HRS2	0.696		
	HRS3	0.842		
	HRS4	0.823		
Organisational Performance	OP1	0.839	0.855	0.663
	OP2	0.836		
	OP3	0.766		
Property Management System	PMS1	0.799	0.875	0.699
	PMS2	0.815		
	PMS3	0.847		
	PMS4	0.881		
Yield Management System	YMS1	0.856	0.848	0.585
	YMS2	0.741		
	YMS3	0.705		
	YMS4	0.748		

Convergent validity, as outlined by Hair et al. (2019), evaluates the extent to which a specific measure aligns with other alternative measures of the same concept and its effectiveness in

capturing the intended concept. In contrast, discriminant validity ensures that the measurement scale is distinct enough from other related variables within the same model. In this study, the assessment of discriminant validity initially involved a comparison of correlations between variables and the square roots of the average variance extracted (AVE), following the guidelines proposed by Fornell and Larcker (1981). According to Fornell and Larcker (1981), for a concept to demonstrate discriminant validity, its square root should exceed the correlations with all other constructs. The examination of relationships between latent components in Table 4.6, with a focus on values in the shaded regions and boldface, confirms the presence of discriminant validity in the study.

Table 4.6: *Discriminant Validity using Fornell and Larcker Criterion*

Constructs	HRS	OP	PMS	YMS
Hotel Reservation System	0.762			
Organisational Performance	0.522	0.814		
Property Management System	0.429	0.524	0.836	
Yield Management System	0.617	0.542	0.623	0.765

4.9.2 Structural Model

The structural model was employed to ascertain the expected relationships between the dependent variable (OP) and the independent variables (HRS, PMS, and YMS). To assess the significance of the direct interaction pathway coefficients for the dataset consisting of 181 data points, a bootstrapping technique was applied. Table 4.7, as established by Hair, Hult, Ringle, and Sarstedt (2014), illustrates the initial basis for this study.

Table 4.7: *Measures and Threshold Values for Assessment of Inner Model*

Assessment Measure	Measure	Threshold
Path Coefficient	T-value	1.96 (p<0.05)
Co-efficient of Determination	R^2	0.17 (weak), 0.33 (moderate) and 0.67(good)
Predictive Relevance	Q^2	0.02 (small), 0.15 (medium) and 0.35 (strong)

Source: Hair et al. (2014).

Figure 4.3: Structural Model

Table 4.8 Path Coefficient

Hypotheses	Relationship	Beta	Standard Error	T-Values	P-Values	Decision
H ₀₁	HRS->OP	0.923	0.089	10.363	0.000*	Rejected
H ₀₂	PMS>OP	0.276	0.096	2.890	0.004*	Rejected
H ₀₃	YMS->OP	0.144	0.072	1.988	0.000*	Rejected

*p<0.05.

The path coefficient for the relationship between Hotel Reservation Management (HRS) and Organizational Performance (OP) is found to be 0.923, with a standard error of 0.089. The T-value is 10.363, and the associated p-value is 0.000, which is less than the common significance threshold of 0.05. This indicates strong statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H₀₁), suggesting that there is a significant positive relationship between the effectiveness of Hotel Reservation Management and Organizational Performance. In simpler terms, as the hotel's

reservation management improves, it leads to a notable enhancement in the overall organizational performance.

The path coefficient for the relationship between Property Management System (PMS) and Organizational Performance (OP) is 0.276, with a standard error of 0.096. The T-value associated with this relationship is 2.890, and the p-value is 0.004, which is less than 0.05. Consequently, we can reject the null hypothesis (H02). This suggests that there is a significant positive relationship between the efficiency of the Property Management System and Organizational Performance. In other words, as the property management system becomes more effective, it contributes positively to the overall organizational performance.

The path coefficient between Yield Management System (YMS) and Organizational Performance (OP) is 0.144, and its standard error is 0.072. The T-value for this relationship is 1.988, and the p-value is 0.000, which is below the 0.05 threshold. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis (H03). This indicates a statistically significant positive relationship between the effectiveness of the Yield Management System and Organizational Performance. In more straightforward terms, when the yield management system is better managed and optimized, it leads to a measurable improvement in the overall performance of the organization.

In summary, the statistical analysis of the path coefficients suggests that all three hypotheses (H01, H02, and H03) are rejected, indicating that Hotel Reservation Management, Property Management System, and Yield Management System all have a significant positive impact on Organizational Performance in the context of the study.

4.10 Coefficient of determination (R^2)

The coefficient of determination, commonly referred to as R-squared (R^2), holds significant importance as a statistical measure. It quantifies the percentage of variation in the dependent variable (OP) that can be attributed to the independent variables (HRS, PMS, and YMS) within a regression model. In more straightforward terms, R-squared serves as an indicator of how

well the independent variables can explain and account for the fluctuations observed in the dependent variable. This metric offers valuable insights into the degree to which the independent variables enhance the model's ability to predict and comprehend the behavior of the dependent variable.

Table 4.9 *Coefficient of Determination (R²)*

Construct	R²
Organisational Performance	0.671

The coefficient of determination, which falls within the range of 0 to 1, serves as a measure of how effectively the independent variables (HRS, PMS, and YMS) within the regression model elucidate the variance present in the dependent variable (OP). In this specific instance, the R² value for the model, which clarifies the variance in OP attributed to HRS, PMS, and YMS, stands at 0.671 (as depicted in Figure 4.1). This R² value of 0.671 signifies that approximately 67.1% of the variability observed in the dependent variable (OP) can be elucidated by the independent variables incorporated in the regression model. To put it differently, the independent variables expound on roughly 67.1% of the variations discernible in the dependent variable. The remaining 32.9% of the variability remains unaccounted for by the independent variables and may be attributed to other factors that have not been considered in the model.

4.11 Effect size (*f*²)

Effect size (*f*²) is a statistical metric employed to gauge the extent of the relationship between independent and dependent variables in a regression analysis. It serves as a valuable tool for evaluating the practical significance or real-world impact of the relationship between variables, going beyond mere statistical significance (Ojeleye, Ojeleye, Karem, & Abdullahi, 2023). In essence, effect size provides insights into how meaningful or substantial the observed relationship is in practical terms, helping researchers and analysts better understand the significance of their findings beyond statistical measures.

$$f^2 = \frac{R^2 \text{ Included} - R^2 \text{ Excluding}}{1 - R^2 \text{ Included}}$$

Effect size (f^2) is determined by dividing the variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variable(s) by the remaining unexplained variance, as previously mentioned. This calculation quantifies the extent to which the independent variable(s) contribute to the observed variability in the dependent variable in comparison to the variability that the model does not account for. In essence, it provides a numerical measure of the relative impact and contribution of the independent variable(s) in explaining the variability observed in the dependent variable.

Table 4.10: *Effect Size (f^2)*

Constructs	f^2 (OP)	Effect Size
HRS	0.976	Large
PMS	0.086	Small
YMS	0.036	Small

Interpreting f^2 values according to Cohen (1988) provides valuable insights into the effect size of independent variables on the dependent variable. A small f^2 value, typically around 0.02, suggests a minor effect size, indicating that the independent variable(s) have a limited impact on the dependent variable. A medium f^2 value, approximately 0.15, indicates a moderate effect size, signifying a more noticeable and substantial influence of the independent variable(s) on the dependent variable. In contrast, a large f^2 value, around 0.35, signifies a substantial effect size, suggesting a strong and significant influence of the independent variable(s) on the dependent variable.

Analyzing Table 4.9 in the context of these interpretations, it appears that PMS and YMS have small effect sizes, implying a small impact on the dependent variable. However, it is noteworthy that HRS has large effect size, indicating that this particular independent variable

does exert a significant influence on the dependent variable in the regression model. This underscores the varying degrees of importance and significance of the different independent variables in explaining the variability observed in the dependent variable.

4.12 Predictive Relevance Assessment (Q^2)

In the context of partial least squares regression, a multivariate analytical method, Q^2 (Q-squared) is a statistical measure employed to assess predictive relevance, as described by Cohen (1988). Q^2 specifically evaluates the predictive accuracy of a PLS model, particularly its capability to make forecasts for the dependent variable(s) using the independent variables. Q^2 is calculated by comparing the model's predictive performance to that of a simple model that predicts the dependent variable(s) based on their mean value. It quantifies the proportion of the dependent variable's variance that the PLS model can predict more effectively than the mean-based model, providing insights into the model's ability to make meaningful predictions.

Figure 4.4: Predictive Relevance

In the context of partial least squares regression, a multivariate analytical method, Q^2 (Q-squared) is a statistical measure employed to assess predictive relevance, as described by Cohen (1988). Q^2 specifically evaluates the predictive accuracy of a PLS model, particularly its capability to make forecasts for the dependent variable(s) using the independent variables. Q-squared is calculated by comparing the model's predictive performance to that of a simple model that predicts the dependent variable(s) based on their mean value. It quantifies the proportion of the dependent variable's variance that the PLS model can predict more effectively than the mean-based model, providing insights into the model's ability to make meaningful predictions.

Table 4.11: *Predictive Relevance(Q²)*

Constructs	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
OP	240.000	149.975	0.375

4.13 Discussion of Findings

This section discusses extensively the study's findings.

H₀₁: Hotel Reservation System (HRS) and Organizational Performance (OP).

The significant effect of hotel reservation systems on the organizational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria is a topic of substantial importance, especially in an era where technology plays a pivotal role in the success of businesses. The finding is in tandem with previous studies of Muktar, Suleiman and Nasiru (2017) and Binuya and Aregbehola (2004).

First and foremost, an effective hotel reservation system can greatly enhance the overall organizational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria. These systems streamline the booking process, allowing for efficient management of room availability and guest preferences. As a result, hotels can optimize their occupancy rates, reduce the risk of overbooking or underbooking, and ensure a smoother guest experience. This, in turn, leads to higher levels of customer satisfaction, which is directly linked to improved organizational performance. Satisfied guests are more likely to return, leave positive reviews, and recommend the hotel to others, all of which contribute to increased revenue and profitability.

Moreover, a well-implemented hotel reservation system can enhance operational efficiency. It automates various administrative tasks, such as managing reservations, processing payments, and generating reports. This reduces the workload on staff and minimizes the chances of errors, allowing employees to focus on providing high-quality services to guests. The efficiency gains translate into cost savings and improved resource allocation, ultimately benefiting the bottom line of hospitality firms.

Additionally, in the competitive landscape of the hospitality industry in Nigeria, having a sophisticated reservation system can give hotels a competitive edge. Travelers often choose hotels based on the convenience and ease of booking, and a user-friendly reservation system can attract more customers. This not only increases occupancy rates but also strengthens the hotel's brand image and reputation.

Furthermore, reservation systems provide valuable data and insights into guest preferences and booking patterns. Hospitality firms can use this data to tailor their services, marketing strategies, and pricing models to better meet the needs and expectations of their target market. This data-driven approach can lead to more effective decision-making, improved customer retention, and ultimately, higher profitability.

In conclusion, the significant effect of hotel reservation systems on the organizational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria cannot be overstated. These systems offer a multitude of benefits, including improved guest satisfaction, enhanced operational efficiency, competitiveness, and data-driven decision-making. By investing in and effectively utilizing modern reservation systems, hospitality firms in Nigeria can not only thrive in a competitive market but also contribute significantly to the country's tourism and economic growth.

H02: Property Management System (PMS) and Organizational Performance (OP).

The significant effect of a Property Management System (PMS) on the organizational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria is a crucial aspect of their operations. PMS plays a pivotal role in the management of various aspects of a hotel or hospitality establishment, and its impact on organizational performance is substantial. The finding is in agreement with previous studies of Hailu (2014) and Olise et al. (2014.)

Firstly, a robust PMS can greatly improve the efficiency of daily operations within a hospitality firm. It streamlines tasks such as guest check-in/check-out, room assignment, billing, and inventory management. This automation reduces the likelihood of errors and ensures a

smoother, more organized workflow. As a result, employees can focus on providing better customer service and addressing guest needs, ultimately leading to increased guest satisfaction. Satisfied guests are more likely to return and recommend the hotel to others, which directly contributes to higher occupancy rates and revenue.

Moreover, an effective PMS provides real-time data and insights into the hotel's performance. Managers and decision-makers can access key metrics, such as occupancy rates, revenue per available room (RevPAR), and guest preferences. This data-driven approach enables hospitality firms to make informed decisions about pricing, marketing strategies, and resource allocation. By optimizing pricing strategies based on demand trends, hotels can maximize revenue, which positively impacts the overall organizational performance.

Additionally, a PMS enhances communication and collaboration among different departments within a hospitality firm. For example, it facilitates better coordination between front desk staff, housekeeping, and maintenance teams. This improved communication ensures that rooms are ready for guests on time and maintenance issues are addressed promptly, leading to smoother operations and higher guest satisfaction.

Furthermore, PMS systems can also assist in managing relationships with third-party booking channels and online travel agencies (OTAs). Integrating with these platforms allows hotels to expand their reach and attract a wider audience of potential guests. Effective management of these channels can result in increased bookings, revenue, and, consequently, better organizational performance.

In the competitive landscape of the Nigerian hospitality industry, having an advanced PMS can be a competitive advantage. It can differentiate a hotel from its competitors by offering guests a seamless and convenient experience. This, in turn, can lead to stronger brand loyalty and a positive reputation in the market.

In conclusion, the significant effect of a Property Management System on the organizational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria is multifaceted. It enhances operational efficiency, provides valuable data for decision-making, improves guest satisfaction, and enables better communication and collaboration. Investing in a modern and effective PMS is not just a technological upgrade but a strategic move that can lead to increased revenue, profitability, and long-term success in the Nigerian hospitality sector.

H03 Yield Management System (YMS) and Organizational Performance (OP).

The significant effect of a Yield Management System (YMS) on the organizational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria is a crucial aspect of modern hotel management. The finding is in congruence with previous studies of Choi and Kimes (2002), Buick (2003) and Abdullahi (2020). Yield Management, often referred to as revenue management, is a strategy that focuses on optimizing pricing and inventory to maximize revenue and profitability.

First and foremost, a well-implemented Yield Management System can lead to substantial revenue growth for hospitality firms in Nigeria. By dynamically adjusting room prices based on factors such as demand, seasonality, and market conditions, hotels can capture the full value of their rooms. This not only increases revenue but also improves the overall financial health of the organization. Increased revenue can be channeled back into the business for improvements, expansions, or upgrades, further enhancing organizational performance.

Furthermore, a YMS allows hotels to make data-driven decisions. It provides insights into booking patterns, market trends, and customer behavior. This data can be used to refine marketing strategies, target specific customer segments, and develop customized promotions. In a competitive industry like hospitality, this ability to tailor offerings to meet the needs of different customer groups is invaluable. It can result in higher occupancy rates and revenue per available room (RevPAR), key indicators of organizational success in the sector.

A Yield Management System also improves operational efficiency. By optimizing pricing and room allocation, hotels can avoid issues like overbooking or underbooking, which can lead to guest dissatisfaction and revenue loss. Additionally, it enables better resource allocation, ensuring that staff and facilities are efficiently utilized. This efficiency contributes to cost savings and higher profitability, directly impacting organizational performance.

Moreover, YMS fosters a culture of strategic thinking and adaptability within hospitality firms. In a rapidly changing market, the ability to respond quickly to fluctuations in demand and market conditions is vital. Yield Management encourages a proactive approach to revenue optimization, enabling hotels to stay competitive and agile in a dynamic industry environment. Lastly, a YMS can enhance customer satisfaction. By offering competitive pricing and tailored promotions, hotels can attract more guests and provide them with a positive booking experience. Satisfied guests are more likely to return and recommend the hotel to others, contributing to repeat business and word-of-mouth marketing. Ultimately, this leads to improved brand reputation and long-term organizational success.

In conclusion, the significant effect of a Yield Management System on the organizational performance of hospitality firms in Nigeria is evident in its ability to drive revenue growth, enhance operational efficiency, support data-driven decision-making, foster adaptability, and improve customer satisfaction. Implementing a YMS is not just a strategic advantage; it is a key driver of success in a competitive and evolving hospitality industry.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

The basic purpose of this chapter is to give the summary, conclusions and recommendation of the study. Furthermore, the limitation of the study was identified and suggestions for further studies was advanced.

5.2. Summary

This study aimed at assessing the influence of information technology on the operational performance of the Nigerian hospitality industry. The findings of the study reveal that both Hotel Reservation Management (HRS) and Property Management System (PMS) significantly influence the organizational performance (OP) of hospitality firms in Nigeria, while the effect of Yield Management System (YMS) on OP is also statistically significant. Specifically, the strong positive path coefficient for HRS suggests that efficient hotel reservation management has a profound and highly beneficial impact on overall organizational performance. Similarly, the positive path coefficient for PMS indicates that an effective property management system contributes positively to OP. Additionally, the positive path coefficient for YMS signifies the significance of a well-managed yield management system in enhancing OP. These results emphasize the critical role of modern systems and technology in optimizing revenue, operational efficiency, and customer satisfaction, all of which are vital for the success of hospitality firms in Nigeria.

5.3 Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings of this study underscore the pivotal role that technology-driven systems, such as Hotel Reservation Management (HRS), Property Management System (PMS), and Yield Management System (YMS), play in shaping the organizational performance (OP) of hospitality firms in Nigeria. The robust statistical evidence supports the hypothesis that

efficient management of hotel reservations, property resources, and revenue through these systems leads to significant positive impacts on overall performance. The importance of these findings lies not only in the potential for revenue growth but also in the enhancement of operational efficiency, data-driven decision-making, adaptability in a competitive market, and the ability to provide guests with a satisfying experience. As the hospitality industry in Nigeria continues to evolve and face various challenges, the adoption and effective utilization of such technology-driven systems emerge as critical strategies for sustained success and competitiveness. Consequently, this study advocates for the continued investment in and integration of these systems as essential tools for the long-term prosperity of hospitality firms in Nigeria.

5.4 Recommendations

The following recommendations are advanced based on the study's findings:

1. Given the strong positive relationship between HRS and OP, hospitality firms in Nigeria should prioritize the enhancement of their hotel reservation management practices. This includes investing in user-friendly reservation systems, training staff to effectively utilize these systems, and regularly updating and optimizing booking processes. By doing so, hotels can ensure a seamless and efficient reservation experience for guests, reduce the risk of overbooking or underbooking, and improve occupancy rates. Moreover, focusing on improving HRS can lead to higher customer satisfaction and repeat business, ultimately contributing to enhanced organizational performance.
2. Based on the significant positive relationship established in Hypothesis 2 between Property Management Systems (PMS) and the organizational performance (OP) of hospitality firms in Nigeria, it is strongly recommended that these firms prioritize the enhancement and optimization of their PMS. This can be achieved through seamless integration with other critical systems, rigorous staff training, strategic data utilization, and the automation of

routine tasks. By doing so, hospitality establishments can maximize the potential of their PMS, streamline operations, and ultimately drive improved organizational performance, which is vital for success and competitiveness in the Nigerian hospitality industry.

3. Given the substantial positive relationship established in Hypothesis 3 between Yield Management Systems (YMS) and the organizational performance (OP) of hospitality firms in Nigeria, it is strongly recommended that these firms prioritize the implementation of effective yield management strategies. This entails adopting advanced YMS technology, conducting continuous market research, maintaining pricing flexibility, providing staff training and education, and vigilantly monitoring performance. By doing so, hospitality establishments can maximize the impact of their YMS, optimize revenue, and ultimately enhance their overall organizational performance, which is essential for success and competitiveness within the dynamic Nigerian hospitality industry.

5.5 Limitations of the Study and Suggestions for Further Study

1. The cross-sectional nature of this study, which captures data at a single point in time, may not fully account for the dynamic nature of the hospitality industry. Response bias and social desirability bias could have influenced survey responses, given the study's reliance on self-reported data. Generalizability of the findings may be limited to the specific context of Nigeria and the hospitality industry in this region.

Future research in this field should consider adopting longitudinal research designs to provide a more comprehensive view of how the relationships between variables evolve over time. Combining quantitative survey data with qualitative methods can deepen understanding by exploring the "why" behind observed relationships. Comparative studies across diverse geographic and industry contexts can uncover unique challenges and opportunities. Research should also explore the environmental and ethical implications of technology adoption in the hospitality sector, keeping pace with emerging technologies and

investigating the impact from the perspective of customers and specific subsectors within the industry.

REFERENCES

- Aaker, D. (2012). Building strong brands. Simon and Schuster.
- Adewoye, J. O. & Akanbi, T. A. (2012). Role of information and communication technology investment on the profitability of small and medium scale industry—a case of sachet water companies in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 3(2): 64-71.
- Appaw-Agbola, E. T., & Agbola, A. K. (2013). Implementing Yield Management in Hotels: An Empirical Study on Small and Medium Hotels in Ghana. *World*,3(3). *Approaches* (p.130-132).
- Archibugi, D., & Coco, A. (2005). Measuring technological capabilities at the country level: A survey and a menu for choice. *Research policy*, 34(2), 175-194.
- Armbrust, M., Fox, A., Griffith, R., Joseph, A. D., Katz, R., Konwinski, A., & Zaharia, M. (2010). A view of cloud computing. *Communications of the ACM*, 53(4), 50-58.
- Armstrong, J. S., & Overton, T. S. (1977). Estimating non response bias mail surveys. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 14, 396–402. <https://doi.org/10.2307/315078>
- Ayatse, F. A. (2012). Impact of information communication technology (Ict) on corporate performance: A case study of cement manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *Global Advanced Research Journal of Management and Business Studies*, 1(18): 259-63.
- Bethapudi, A (2013). *Journal Of applied economics and business*, Vol11, issue 4 – December 2013, 67-79
- Bowie, D., & Buttle, F. (2013). Hospitality marketing. Routledge.
- Buhalis, D. (2003). E-Tourism: Information technology for strategic tourism management. Pearson Education.
- Buhalis, D. & Main, H. (1998). Information technology in peripheral small and medium

- hospitality enterprises: Strategic analysis and critical factors. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 10 (5), 198–202.
- Choi, S., & Kimes, S. E. (2002). Electronic distribution channels' effect on hotel revenue management. The Cornell hotel and restaurant. *Administration Quarterly*, 43(3), 23-31.
- Churchill, D. (1991). Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods
- Cobanoglu, Cihan, Kadir Corbaci, & Bill Ryan. (2001). A comparative study: the impact of technology in lodging properties in the United States and Turkey. *International Journal of Hospitality Information Technology* 2(1), 23-40.
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences* (2nd ed.). New York: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Publishers.
- Curran, J. M., Meuter, M. L., & Surprenant, C. F. (2003). Intentions to use self-service technologies: A confluence of multiple attitudes. *Journal of Service Research: JSR*, 5(3), 209-224.
- Davenport, T. H. (2013). *Process innovation: reengineering work through information technology*. Harvard Business Press.
- David, J., Grabski, S. & Kasavana, M. (1996) The productivity paradox of Hotel-Industry Technology. *The Cornell Hotel and Restaurant Administration Quarterly*, 37 (2), 64-70.
- DiRomauldo, A., & Gurbaxani, V. (1998). Strategic intent for IT outsourcing. Center for Research on Information Technology and Organizations.
- Doganis, R. (2002). *Flying off course: The economics of international airlines*. Psychology Press.
- Doll, W. (2004). Information technology's strategic impact on the American air travel service
- Eichhorn, B. R. (2014). *Common Method Variance Techniques*. Cleveland OH: Cleveland State University.
- Field, A. (2017). *Discovering Statistics Using IBM SPSS Statistics* (5th ed.). London: SAGE

Publications, Inc.

- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error: algebra and statistics. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(3), 382–388. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3150980>
- Fuller, C. M., Simmering, M. J., Atinc, G., Atinc, Y., & Babin, B. J. (2015). Common methods variance detection in business research. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(8), 3192–3198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2015.12.008>
- Ghobadian, A., Speller, S., & Jones, M. (1994). Service quality: concepts and models. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 11(9), 43-66.
- Gichoya, D. (2005). Factors affecting the successful implementation of IT projects in government. *The Electronic Journal of e-Government*, 3(4), 175-184.
- Ham, S., Kim, W. & Jeong, S. (2005). Effect of information technology on performance in upscale hotels, *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 24 (2), 281-294.
- Hsieh, L. F., & Lin, L. H. (2010). A performance evaluation model for international tourist hotels in Taiwan-An application of the relational network DEA. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 29(1), 14-24.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2010). *Multivariate Data Analysis: A Global Perspective* (7th, illustr ed.). New Jersey: Pearson Education.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2019). *Multivariate Data Analysis* (8th ed.). Hampshire: Cengage Learning EMEA.
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). *Sage Publisher*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-10-2013-0128>
- Hair, J. F., Page, M., & Brunsveld, N. (2020). *Essentials of Business Research Methods* (4th ed.). New York: Routledge.

- Hartmann, N. (2019). *Common method bias: what is, why is it important and what you can do to mitigate and control it*. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4A3OwwdJnXQ>
- Hulland, J. (1999). Use of partial least squares (PLS) in strategic management research: a review of four recent studies. *Strategic Management Journal*, 20, 195–204. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0266\(199902\)20:2<195::AID-SMJ13>3.0.CO;2-7](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0266(199902)20:2<195::AID-SMJ13>3.0.CO;2-7)
- Inman, R. A., Sale, R. S., Green Jr, K. W., & Whitten, D. (2011). Agile manufacturing: relation to JIT, operational performance and firm performance. *Journal of Operations Management*, 29(4), 343-355.
- Ip, Crystal, Rosanna Leung, and Rob Law (2011). Progress and development of information and communication technologies in hospitality." *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management* 23(4), 533-551.
- Ives, B., Hamilton, S., & Davis, G. B. (1980). A framework for research in computer-based management information systems. *Management Science*, 26(9), 910-934.
- Jacobs, M. A., & Swink, M. (2011). Product portfolio architectural complexity and operational performance: Incorporating the roles of learning and fixed assets. *Journal of Operations Management*, 29(7), 677-691.
- Kock, N. (2015). Common method bias in PLS-SEM : A full collinearity assessment approach. *Internal Journal of E-Collaboration*, 11(4), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijec.2015100101>
- Khan, L. (1993). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*,
- Kim, Y. G., Eves, A., & Scarles, C. (2013). Empirical verification of a conceptual model of local food consumption at a tourist destination. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 33, 484-489.
- Kinyua, R. K. (2012). Role of technology in building sustainable competitive advantage: A

- case study of hotels in Nakuru (Doctoral dissertation).
- Knezek, G., & Christensen, R. (2002). Impact of new information technologies on teachers and students. In *networking the Learner* (pp. 169-178). Springer US.
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 4th Edition, New Age International. New Delhi, pp.12-15.
- Lambert, D. M., & Harrington, T. C. (1989). Establishing customer service strategies within the marketing mix: More empirical evidence. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 10(2), 44–60. Retrieved from [researchgate.net/publication/282673316](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/282673316)
- Laudon, K. C., & Laudon, J. P. (2011). *Essentials of management information systems*. Upper Saddle River: Pearson.
- Law, R., Leung, R., & Buhalis, D. (2009). Information technology applications in hospitality and tourism: A review of publications from 2005 to 2007. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 26(5-6), 599-623.
- Lee, C. (2001). An analytical framework for evaluating e-commerce business models and strategies." *Internet Research* 11(4), 349-359.
- Lehtinen, J., & Tuomas A. (2010). Is performance measurement suitable for an extended enterprise?" *International Journal of Operations & Production Management* 30(2), 181-204.
- Levitt, T. (1972). Production-line approach to service. *Harvard Business Review* 50(5), 41-52. London. Eps.
- Lindner, J. R., Murphy, T. H., & Briers, G. E. (2001). Handling nonresponse in social research. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 42(4), 43–53. <https://doi.org/10.5032/jae.2001.04043>
- Malhotra, M. K., & Grover, V. (1998). An assessment of survey research in POM: From constructs to theory. *Journal of Operations Management*, 16(4), 407–425. <https://doi.org/10.5688/aj720243>

- Mihalic, T., & Buhalis, D. (2013). ICT as a new competitive advantage factor—case of small transitional hotel sector. *Economic and Business Review*, 15(1), 33-56.
- Monge, P., & Fulk, J. (1999). Communication technology for global network organizations. *Shaping organizational form: Communication, connection, and community*, 71-100.
- Moyo, L. M. (1996). Information technology strategies for Africa's survival in the twenty-first century: IT all pervasive. *Information Technology for Development*, 7(1), 17-27.
- Mpofu, K. C., & Watkins-Mathys, L. (2011). Understanding ICT adoption in the small firm sector in Southern Africa. *Journal of Systems and Information Technology*, 13(2), 179-199.
- Neely, A., Gregory, M., & Platts, K. (1995). Performance measurement system design: a literature review and research agenda. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 15(4), 80-116.
- Njenga, J., & Alexander, J. (2012). East African Tourism Opportunities for the Finnish Market: Development of Joint Marketing Strategy for the Nordic Travel Fair 2013. 48
- Onasanya, S. A., Shehu, R. A., Oduwaiye, R. O. and Shehu, L. A. (2010). Higher institutions lecturers' attitude towards integration of ICT into teaching and research in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Information Technology*, 2(1): 1-10.
- Onu, C. A., Ibrahim, O. O. and Segun, F. K. (2015). Effect of information technology investment on organizational productivity and growth of small and medium scale enterprises in developing countries. *Business and Economics Journal*, 6(3): 1.
- Papazoglou, M. P., & Van Den Heuvel, W. J. (2007). Service oriented architectures: approaches, technologies and research issues. *The VLDB journal*, 16(3), 389-415.
- Parkan, C. (1996). Measuring the performance of hotel operations. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, 30(4), 257-292.
- Porter, L., & Tanner, S. (Eds.). (2012). *Assessing business excellence*. Routledge.

- Porter, M. E., & Millar, V. E. (1985). How information gives you competitive advantage.
- Rodionov, E. N., Thomas, A. W., & Londergan, J. T. (1994). Charge asymmetry of parton distributions. *Modern Physics Letters A*, 9(19), 1799-1806.
- Podsakoff, P. M., Mackenzie, S. B., Lee, J., & Podsakoff, N. P. (2003). Common method biases in behavioral research: A critical review of the literature and recommended remedies. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(5), 879–903. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.88.5.879>
- Rummler, G. A., & Brache, A. P. (2012). *Improving performance: How to manage the whitespace on the organization chart*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Ryus, P. (2010). *A Methodology for Performance Measurement and Peer Comparison in the Public Transportation Industry* (Vol. 141). Transportation Research Board.
- Sahadev, S., & Nazrul I., (2005). Why hotels adopt ITs: a study on the IT adoption propensity of hotels in Thailand." *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management* 17(5), 391-401.
- Samkange, F. (2008). *Adaptation, Implementation and Utilisation IT in the Hospitality Industry: Trends and Perspectives from a Developing Country*.
- Seethamraju, R. (2012). Business process management: a missing link in business education. *Business Process Management Journal*, 18(3), 532-547.
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research Method for Business: A Skill Building Approach* (7th ed.). Chichester: John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- Shi, Fangmin, Alastair Gale, and Kevin Purdy." Helping people with IT device control by eye gaze." *Computers Helping People with Special Needs*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2006.480-487.
- Shirazi, F., Roya G., & Dolores A. H. (2009). The impact of information and communication technology (IT), education and regulation on economic freedom in Islamic Middle Eastern

- countries." *Information & Management* 46(8), 426-433. 49
- Siguaw, A., Enz, A. & Namasivayam, K. (2000) Adoption of information technology in US hotels: strategically driven objectives. *Journal of Travel Research*, 39 (2), 192-201.
- Suleiman, B., Sakr, S., Jeffery, R., & Liu, A. (2012). On understanding the economics and elasticity challenges of deploying business applications on public cloud infrastructure. *Journal of Internet Services and Applications*, 3(2), 173-193.
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2012). Using multivariate statistics (6th ed.). In *New York: Harper and Row*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/022267>
- Twining, P. (2002). Conceptualizing computer use in education: introducing the computer Practice Framework (CPF). *British Educational Research Journal*, 28(1), 95-110.
- Webster, F. (2014). Theories of the information society. Routledge.
- Werthner H., Klein S, Information technology and tourism—A challenging relationship Springer, New York (1999)
- Yusuf, M (2013). The Impact of Management Information System (MIS) on the Performance of Business Organization in Nigeria. Diss. University of Abuja.
- Zorn, T. E., Flanagan, A. J., & Shoham, M. D. (2011). Institutional and no institutional influences on information and communication technology adoption and use among nonprofit organizations. *Human Communication Research*, 37(1), 1-33.